

Single Site W(0) versus Re(I)-Dipyridophenazine- Based Conjugated Porous Polymer for CO₂ Photoreduction

Ángela Matarín, Félix Sánchez, Laura Collado, Mariam Barawi, Victor A. de la Peña O'Shea, Avelina Arnanz,* Marta Liras,* and Marta Iglesias*

Herein, the synthesis and characterization of two robust tungsten and rhenium carbonyl complexes integrated into an organic polymer (CPP-Re, CPP-W) are reported. These polymers are obtained by a Suzuki coupling reaction between the corresponding dibromo metal-carbonyl substituted dipyrido[3,2-a:2',3'-c]phenazine complex and 1,3,5-triphenylbenzene-4',4'',4''',4''''-triboronic acid and integrated catalytic active sites and photosensitizer since they have not only nitrogen sites to coordinate metal active centers as rhenium or tungsten but photoactive units with good charge-separating ability which can significantly improve the CO₂ photoreduction reaction (CO₂PRR). These polymers show similar activity in solid-gas CO₂PRR in absence of sacrificial agents to produce syn gas (CO + H₂) but CPP-W selectivity to products change regarding CPP-Re being able to produce also large amount of more demanding electron products such as methane and ethane. Moreover, the single-site Re- or W-CPP catalysts could prevent the dimerization of complexes that produces its deactivation. This work shows the potential of CPPs as matrices to support single active centers for heterogeneous catalysis.

capable of mitigating the effects of greenhouse gases as the main causes of global warming. The significance of these actions was reflected in the *Paris Agreement on Climate Change* (COP21)^[1] and ratified at rest conferences (COP22-COP27). It was agreed to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 40–70% in 2050 compared to 2010 to limit the temperature increase below 2 °C to 2100 compared to the preindustrial era as a needed measure to avoid even more severe climatic catastrophes. To achieve this ambitious objective, two main strategies are needed: 1) the reduction of CO₂ anthropogenic emission, principally from fossil fuel consumption; and 2) the use of CO₂ as raw material. Considering the high stability of the CO₂ molecule, it is necessary to use renewable energy sources to carry out its activation and conversion. In this sense, one of the processes of greatest

1. Introduction

From an environmental point of view, one of the most important challenges for today's society is the development of technologies

interest from the environmental point of view is the production of chemical products and solar fuels through artificial photosynthesis (AP). Thus, CO₂ photoreduction reaction (CO₂PRR) as solar energy storage technology is a promising way for the valorization of CO₂ emissions.

Á. Matarín, M. Iglesias
Instituto de Ciencia de Materiales de Madrid (ICMM-CSIC)
Sor Juana Inés de la Cruz, 3, Cantoblanco, Madrid 28049, Spain
E-mail: marta.iglesias@icmm.csic.es

F. Sánchez
Instituto de Química Orgánica General (IQOG-CSIC)
C/Juan de la Cierva 3, Madrid 28006, Spain

L. Collado, M. Barawi, V. A. de la Peña O'Shea, M. Liras
IMDEA Energía
Av. Ramon de la Sagra 3, Mostoles 28935, Spain
E-mail: marta.liras@imdea.org

A. Arnanz
Departamento de Química inorgánica
Universidad Autónoma de Madrid
Cantoblanco, Madrid 28049, Spain
E-mail: avi.arnanz@uam.es

 The ORCID identification number(s) for the author(s) of this article can be found under <https://doi.org/10.1002/ssstr.202400185>.

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As it was pointed out before, the CO₂ molecule is very stable showing a high carbonyl bond dissociation energy (750 kJ mol⁻¹). From the thermodynamic point of view, in the gas phase the direct photodissociation of CO₂ molecule is really unfavourable due to the high negative redox potential of CO₂/CO₂^{•-} (-1.90 V vs NHE, at pH 7.00). However, proton-assisted CO₂ photoreduction is easier because of the relatively lower potential (from -0.24 to -0.61 vs NHE, at pH 7.00), but leading to different products in function of the electron involved: CO (2e⁻), HCHO (4e⁻), CH₃OH (6e⁻), or CH₄ (8e⁻), among others.^[2]

In this sense, homogeneous photocatalysts for CO₂ reduction based on molecular transition metal complexes of Co(II), Ru(II), Ir(III), or Re(I) have been reported.^[3,4] These complexes coordinate CO₂ and can also transfer multiple electrons, eluding the high-energy CO₂ anion radical intermediate. Among them, Re-complexes (fac-Re(NN)(CO)₃X, NN = diimine, X = Cl, Br) are interesting examples which have been efficient applied for selective obtention of carbon monoxide from carbon dioxide.^[5–9] These complexes have problems as their instability (bimetallic decomposition) or reduced absorption in the visible region.^[10] To overcome such limitations, heterogenization of molecular

complexes on different organic, inorganic or hybrids supports improves the durability of active centers.^[11–15]

Conjugated porous polymers (CPPs) and, also, covalent organic framework (COFs), which could be considered as subgroup materials of the first with crystalline properties, made through covalent bonds between structural building units (SBUs) have high surface areas and may consist of monomers with singular functional groups. This means that CPPs can be applied in a wide range of applications such as sensors,^[16,17] molecular sieving,^[18] separation and gas adsorption,^[19] photovoltaics^[20] or heterogeneous catalysis.^[21,22] CPPs exhibit good light harvesting and charge conduction properties, high photochemical stability and high surface area that made them ideal to be used as photocatalysis.^[23–29] For this reason, CPPs have been considered a ground-breaking materials for solar energy conversion.^[30] While CPPs have been wide applied as photocatalysts for the hydrogen production from water,^[31,32] they has been much less used for CO₂PRR.^[13]

There are three main ways to prepare CPPs single-site photocatalysts according to as the active unit is incorporated into the framework: non-bonded (encapsulated into the CPP), covalently tethered to the support (usually postsynthesis), and by direct integration of the catalyst into the backbone (generally metalloporphyrines).^[33–35] A common strategy to obtain CPPs active at CO₂PRR in most cases involves the heterogenization of Re-complexes taking advantage of the presence of dipyridine,^[10,15,36–43] triazine,^[44] or phenanthroline^[9] moieties within CPPs molecular structure in a post-synthetic pathway. This kind of materials has been named as metal organic conjugated (micro)porous polymer (MO-CMP) by Cooper et al.^[45] and they have been used as supports for different transition metal complexes. However, to the best of our knowledge, there are no examples in which Re complexes have been used as building units to obtain polymers with such units integrated during the synthesis process of CPP.

In spite of the large number of examples of metal organic CPPs with a supported Re-complex, there are not examples of W-complex for CO₂PRR. However, at molecular level, M(CO)₄(diimine) complexes (M = Cr, Mo, and W) combine electron-rich, low-valent, d⁶ metal atoms stabilized by four carbonyl groups along with the good π*-acceptor character of an α-diimine ligand.^[46] These group 6-complexes have a wide oxidation state window (from a high (VI) to a low (0)) which is why they are good candidates to support CO₂RR via electrocatalysis.^[47,48]

Tungsten and Rhenium are consecutive element in the periodic table, from group 6 and group 7, respectively (Figure 1). This

means that W(0) and Re(I) complex are isoelectronic and we wonder if the probed photocatalytic activity of Rhenium complex to the photoreduction of CO₂ could be extended to W-complex. Furthermore, the use of W-organic CPPs for CO₂PRR could offer several advantages. Attending to the data related with life cycle assessment (LCA) and scalability in the supply of chemical elements for renewable energy,^[48–50] the differences between W and Re elements are important enough (Figure 1): 1) the annual production of W is 1.6-fold higher than the annual production of Re; 2) the global warming potential, attending to the logarithmic of mass of CO₂ produced per mass of element extracted, is more that 35-fold higher for Re than W; 3) W is around 20% cheaper than Re; and 4) the human toxicity potential of W is three order of magnitude less than the human toxicity potential of Re. From the four point of view showed here, W seems to be better option than Re in order to design metal organic CPPs. All of this justify far away the work here presented.

In this article, we have synthesized the W(CO)₄(dipyridophenazine) complex and incorporated it into a CPP by direct metal incorporation by copolymerization to evaluate its performance as a catalyst in CO₂PRR by comparing its behavior with the related Re(CO)₃Br(dipyrido-phenazine) group 7 complex. To do so, dibromo metal-carbonyl substituted dipyr-ido[3,2-a:2',3'-c]phenazine complexes have been the moieties of choice to link with 1,3,5-triphenylbenzene-4',4'',4''',4''''-triboronic acid and 4,4'-diiodo-1,1'-biphenyl, as co-monomer, under Suzuki–Miyaura cross-coupling reaction. Both materials have been extensively characterized. **CPP-W** not only is the first example in the literature of a heterogenized CPP material based on tungsten but also shows similar photocatalytic activity in the CO₂PRR and higher selectivity to electron demanding product as methane and ethane than its **CPP-Re** counterpart.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Synthesis of W(Br₂phenazine)(CO₄) (2), Re(Br₂phenazine)(CO₃) (3) Monomers

Phenanthroline ligands are known by its rich coordination chemistry. In this work, 3,8-dibromodipyrido[3,2-a:2',3'-c]phenazine (1) was obtained from 3,8-dibromo-1,10-phenanthroline-5,6-dione^[51] and *o*-phenylenediamine, following a modification of the reported procedure,^[52,53] (Scheme S1, Supporting Information) and subsequent used as ligand for the preparation of W- and Re-carbonyl complex monomers (2 and 3, respectively) (Scheme 1, see the synthesis details in the Supporting Information).

Figure 1. Cartoon of W and Re elements showing the atomic number, the logarithm of annual production (Kg/year), the logarithm of market price (\$/kg), global warming potential (kg_{CO₂} per kg of element), and the cradle-to-gate human toxicity potential (CTUh/kg_{em}—comparative toxicity unit for human per kilogram emitted). Adapted from reference.^[48]

Scheme 1. Synthesis of W- and Re-carbonyl complex monomers. a) W(CO)₆, b) Re(CO)₅Br.

These W- and Re-monomers **2** and **3** were synthesized from **1** and the corresponding metal-carbonyl complex, W(CO)₆ or Re(CO)₅Br, through a substitution reaction of two carbonyl ligands from the organometallic precursor by the phenazine-type ligand. Re(CO)₅Br complex was prepared from Re₂(CO)₁₀ by a binuclear oxidative addition reaction with Br₂.^[54] W-complex presents an octahedral environment around the W atom with *cis*-arrangement. The ¹H NMR spectrum of **2** (Figure S6, Supporting Information) shows four signals, in the aromatic region, corresponding to the eight chemically equivalent protons of the phenazine-type ligand, with values of the ¹H–¹H coupling constants that are in accordance with their positions in the molecule. Since W-complex is rather insoluble in common organic solvents, this complex was also characterized by solid-state ¹³C-NMR where eleven signals can be distinguished of which those corresponding to the CO ligands appear at δ 213.1 and 200.9 ppm (Figure S6, Supporting Information). The FTIR spectrum shows four strong absorptions in the carbonyl stretching region at 2006, 1901 (shoulder), 1888, and 1823 cm⁻¹, in accordance with *cis*-L₂M(CO)₄ isomerism (C_{2v} symmetry), along with the other bands typical of ligand precursor indicated above (Figure S7, Supporting Information). The mass spectrum shows the presence of the peak corresponding to the ion (M⁺ - CO) whose experimental isotopic distribution coincides with the theoretical one (Figure S7, Supporting Information).

Re-complex presents an octahedral environment around the metal atom, Re(CO)₃L₂X-type, with the possibility of *fac* or *mer* arrangement. The ¹H NMR spectrum of **3** is similar to that of the tungsten analog complex, four signals can be observed in the aromatic region, corresponding to the eight chemically equivalent protons of the phenazine-type ligand. It is worth noting the splitting of the signals at δ 9.95 and 9.47 ppm, possibly due to the coexistence of the *fac* and *mer* isomers in this complex (Figure S8, Supporting Information, left). Since the

complex is poorly soluble in common organic solvents, this complex was also characterized by solid-state ¹³C-NMR where aromatic carbon signals can be distinguished and those corresponding to the CO ligands appears at δ 199.0 and 189.0 ppm (Figure S8, Supporting Information, right). The FTIR spectrum shows three strong and broad bands in the carbonyl stretching region at 2026, 1917, and 1901 cm⁻¹, that could correspond to the result of the overlap of *fac*-L₂XM(CO)₃ (C_{3v} symmetry) and *mer*-L₂XM(CO)₃ (C_{2v} symmetry) isomers, according to what was describe above for the ¹H NMR spectrum of **3**. In addition, other bands typical of ligand precursor were observed (Figure S2, Supporting Information right). The mass spectrum shows the presence of the peak corresponding to the molecular ion whose experimental isotopic distribution coincides with the theoretical one.

2.2. Synthesis and Characterization of Porous Polymers CPP-W, CPP-Re

Metal organic frameworks (MOFs)^[55] and covalent–organic frameworks (COFs)^[34,43] have been applied as photo and electro-catalysts for CO₂RR. Nevertheless, porous conjugated organic materials as CPPs, have been much less studied for such reaction.^[42] The characteristics of CPPs, such as their high stability (chemical and thermal), the versatility of the monomers that can be incorporated into their structure, the π -conjugation along the lattice can facilitate charge migration to the active centers coupled with the possibility of incorporating transition metal complexes acting as redox centers makes these materials excellent photocatalyst candidates for efficient and selective CO₂RR.

CPPs based on W- and Re-carbonyl complexes, **CPP-W** and **CPP-Re**, have been synthesized by a C-C Suzuki–Miyaura cross-coupling reaction in which compounds **2**, or **3** and 4,4'-diiodo-1,1'-biphenyl as co-monomer react with 1,3,5-triphenylbenzene-4',4'',4''',4'''-triboronic acid in different ratios in the presence of Pd(PPh₃)₄ as catalyst, and Cs₂CO₃ as base (**Scheme 2**). The equivalent relation between di-halogen/tri-boronic was 1.5:1 in both cases. CPPs were synthesized from 0.15 eq. of compound **2** or **3** and 1.35 eq. 4,4'-diiodo-1,1'-biphenyl at the feed affording **CPP-W** and **CPP-Re**, respectively. Once synthesized and purified the solids were treated with KCN in a mixture acetone/water to eliminate the Pd(0) residues. The metal contents were determined by inductively coupled plasma-optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) being 0.16 mmol g⁻¹ (**CPP-W**), 0.21 mmol g⁻¹ (**CPP-Re**) indicative of a great control in the feed composition. ICP-OES also confirms that Pd is totally removed from the polymers. Resulting polymers are amorphous, as can be seen in the powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) pattern (Figure S10, Supporting Information). Also, they are air and water stable and insoluble in most standard organic solvents. By elemental analysis their composition meets with those calculated from the feed with the expected errors of the technique (Table S1, Supporting Information).

The structure of both metal-carbonyl-CPPs was determinate by means of FT-IR and solid-state ¹³C-CP/MAS NMR spectroscopies. The integrity of the complex unit within the polymers networks was demonstrated by means FT-IR (**Figure 2a**) showing

Scheme 2. Synthesis of metal organic CPPs based on a) W and b) Re.

the CO ligands of Re(I)- or W(0)-coordinated moieties identified by the characteristic carbonyl stretching vibration between 2100 and 1800 cm^{-1} . Due to the low proportion of complex within the framework this signal can be only be appreciate with a magnification of the spectrum (see both inset at Figure 2a). For the unequivocal characterization, a sample with an incremental amount of Re complex (metal content: 0.60 mmol g^{-1}) was synthesized, **CPP-Re1** (see synthetic and characterization details at supplementary, Table S1 and Figure S11, Supporting Information).

The solid-state ^{13}C -RMN spectra of both type of polymers (Figure 2b) show similar pattern with signals between 115 and 155 ppm that correspond to carbons corresponding to the different aromatic rings. However, the signals from carbonyl groups around 200 ppm are not visible. This could be explained in term of shielding effect because the carbonyl signals are bound to metal nuclei. Even for **CPP-Re1** with a higher amount of Re-carbonyl monomer (1:1 equivalent proportion between 3 and the halogenated monomer at the feed) the carbonyl signals are shielded and does not appear in the spectra (Figure S11, Supporting Information, right).

The porous properties of polymers synthesized have been studied by means of N_2 sorption isotherm analysis at 77 K (Figure 2c). Thus, both N_2 isotherms show a type I profile (IUPAC classification^[56]) corresponding to microporous materials. It can be seen that the curves have hysteresis, this fact is common in porous organic polymers due to partially swelling of the networks during sorption process.^[57] The specific surface area calculated by Brunauer–Emmett–Teller theory (S_{BET}) are 18 and 211 $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$ for **CPP-W** and **CPP-Re**, respectively (Table 1). The pore size distribution (Figure S12, Supporting

Information, DFT method) was estimated as 7.2 and 7.5 nm for **CPP-W** and **CPP-Re**, respectively.

The thermal stability of the polymers was evaluated by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) under air. It can be seen in Figure 2d both polymers have high thermal stability, with **CPP-W** being stable up to 532 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and **CPP-Re** decomposes at 500 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. In both cases the thermal degradation takes place in only one step.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images confirm the porosity of the materials (Figure 2e,f). Both have an irregular surface, especially **CPP-W**, which also shows spherical aggregates. On the contrary, by EDX it has been possible to confirm that the metals W and Re are found in the structure of the respective polymers and that no Pd from the catalyst remains in the polymer (Figure S14 and S15, Supporting Information). Furthermore, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was used to analyze the surface composition and chemical states of the polymers (Figure S16, Supporting Information). In both cases the presence of C and O has been detected, as expected. However, in none of the cases has the presence of Re and W either N been detected. This tells us that, at least in the first nm (around 10) of the sample, these elements are not found. To verify this, high-resolution XPS analysis were carried out in the regions where we would expect to see these elements, without being able to identify them in any of the cases. Despite not having been able to identify Re and W on the surface of the polymers through XPS, X-ray absorption near edge structure (XANES) spectra at Re and W K-edges were acquired and confirmed the presence of these elements in the polymer structure. In principle, this information suggests that the elements and so, the whole metal complexes, are located in the core/bulk of the material and not on its surface.

Figure 2. Characterization of CPPs-M: a) FT-IR; b) ^{13}C -NMR; c) N_2 isotherm; d) TGA, and e, f) SEM images of **CPP-Re** and **CPP-W**, respectively. Note that the data corresponding to **CPP-W** appear in green and **CPP-Re** appears in pink.

Table 1. Porous properties of polymers.

Entry	Material	Metal [%] ^{a)}	S_{BET} [$\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$] ^{b)}	V [$\text{cm}^3 \text{g}^{-1}$] ^{c)}	Pore size [nm]
1	CPP-W	3.0	18	0.039	7.2
2	CP-Re	3.9	211	0.25	7.3

^{a)} Calculated by ICP. ^{b)} At P/Po: 0.99. ^{c)} Calculated from the N_2 adsorption isotherm.

The XANES spectra are primarily used to identify the presence of Re and W in the polymer's matrix. The **Figure 3a** exhibit Re L3-edge and **Figure 3b** exhibit W L3-edge XANES and can be used to confirm the average oxidation state of them into the polymer. The spectrum of **CMP-Re** at L3-edge reveals a profile similar to that described for Re(I)-carbonyl complexes,^[58] with a weak pre-edge, the white-line at $\approx 10.538 \text{ keV}$ and a shoulder on the high-energy side. The spectrum of **CMP-W** shows a white-line peak maximum at $\approx 10.209 \text{ keV}$ as in reported W(0) complexes.^[59]

Solid state UV-Vis absorption spectra show that both polymers have broad absorptions below 400 nm with a

metal-to-ligand charge transfer (MLCT) at 526 nm (**CPP-W**) and 506 nm (**CPP-Re**) (**Figure S17**, Supporting Information). Time-dependent density functional theory (TD-DFT) calculations were used to determine the electronic vertical transitions (**Table S3** and **S4**, Supporting Information) as well as their match with the absorption profile (**Figure 4a,b**). Our studies reveal that W and Re complexes are directly implied in light-mediated charge-transfer processes. TD-DFT calculations indicate that the electronic transitions at the reaction radiation (365 nm, see *vide infra*) in the case of **CPP-W** involve a charge transfer mainly from 1,3,5-triphenylbenzene structural unit to W-ligand both to W-CO bonds and dipyridophenazine moiety (**Figure S19**, Supporting Information). On the contrary, in the case of **CPP-Re**, in addition to the transitions observed in the case of W, new ones appear involving Re-Br to Re-CO bonds (**Figure S20**, Supporting Information). The apparent bandgap energy (E_{gap}) was calculated from Tauc plot using Kubelka-Munk function equation, $F(R)$, assuming direct transition (**Figure 4c**) and obtained by UV-visible diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (DRS) (**Figure S18**, Supporting Information). These E_{gap} values were 3.1 and 2.5 eV for **CPP-W** and **CPP-Re**, respectively. In contrast, electrochemical measurements have been carried out to

Figure 3. XANES spectra at Re L3-edge and W L3- edge in a) CMP-Re and b) CPP-W.

Figure 4. a,b) Absorbance spectra and vertical transitions calculated by TD-DFT of CPPs; b) tauc plots; c,d) cyclic voltammetry of CPPs, and e) electronic band structure comparing with products potentials of **CPP-Re** (magenta) and **CPP-W** (dark green), including the water and CO₂ redox couples at pH = 0.

determine the electronic structure of the polymers. Figure 4d,e show the cyclic voltammetry obtained using the polymers as working electrode. The anodic and cathodic potentials have been explored, allowing the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) position determination of both polymers, being -4.19 eV for **CPP-Re** and -3.54 eV for **CPP-W** (see details in SI about the procedure to correct the potential values and get this position). In the case of the oxidation potentials, they were probably placed in potential ranges where we lost the potential window of the electrolyte. For this reason, the LUMO position and optical band gaps energy determined previously have been used to determine the electronic structure of the two polymers (Figure 4f).

2.3. CO₂ Photoreduction

Homogeneous catalysts such as the $[\text{Re}(\text{bpy})(\text{CO})_3\text{X}]$ complex are well studied for CO₂ reduction (electro- and photocatalytic) as mentioned in the introduction. Their immobilization on different inorganic and organic supports provides stability and allows their recyclability. However, in general, the main CO₂ reduction product obtained is CO. Immobilization of effective transition metal complexes on a suitable support can induce CO₂RR leading to products such as CH₄ or C₂H₆. On the contrary, most CO₂RR studies using this type of material are performed in liquid-phase and in the presence of a sacrificial agent such as Triethanolamine. In contrast, this work investigates the

Figure 5. Cumulative production of **CPP-Re** a) and **CPP-W**, b) in the gas-phase CO₂ photoreduction reaction with water under 15 h of UV illumination ($\lambda_{\max} = 369$ nm). c) CH₄ (triangles) and C₂H₆ (circles) evolution rates, expressed per gram of metal, for **CPP-W** and **CPP-Re**. d) Comparison of the selectivity to C-based products (%). The error bars are estimated as 5%.

photocatalytic CO₂ reduction activity of **CPP-W** and **CPP-Re** using a solid–gas reaction system, which has not been reported before for immobilized metal complex catalysts. Here, gas-phase CO₂ photoreduction with water experiments has been evaluated under UV illumination (Figure S21, Supporting Information), in the absence of any sacrificial agent or any metal co-catalyst.

Both polymers were mainly active for syngas production (i.e., CO and H₂), also delivering minor amounts of CH₄ and C₂H₆ (Figure 5a,b). Interestingly, the CO₂ photoreduction performance of **CPP-W** was 9.6 and 6.5-times higher than that of **CPP-Re** in terms of CH₄ and C₂H₆ production, respectively. In particular, the introduction of W in the CPP led to maximum production rates of ≈ 4.8 and $11.4 \mu\text{mol h}^{-1} \text{g}_{\text{metal}}^{-1}$ for CH₄ and C₂H₆, respectively (Figure 5c), which was accompanied by a noticeable change of selectivity of C-products (Figure 5d). In particular, **CPP-Re** was 94% selective to CO while this selectivity decreased to 58% in **CPP-W**, promoting the formation of more electron-demanding products, such as CH₄ (14%) and C₂H₆ (29%). In order to discard a possible contribution of the organic decomposition of the polymer on the C production, we performed a control experiment in the absence of CO₂ and under UV illumination (see SI for details), in which no carbon product could be detected. Besides, the FTIR spectra (Figure S25, Supporting Information) before and after CO₂ photoreduction tests did not show any evident change, thus confirming the photostability of the photocatalysts under reaction.

It is interesting to note that both polymers showed an increasing trend of CO and H₂ evolution rates after 6 h of UV

illumination (Figure S22, Supporting Information), which coincided with a decrease in CH₄ and C₂H₆ yields. This behaviour is associated with a partial oxidation or photoreforming of products in the presence of water.^[60]

The comparison of the activity of both polymers in terms of photonic efficiency (ζ) also highlights the beneficial effect of W over Re for CO₂ photoreduction, reaching a value of $\zeta = 0.01\%$, almost double than that of **CPP-Re** (0.005%). The improvement in the photocatalytic activity of **CPP-W** versus **CPP-Re** could be explained in terms of band gap engineering. As it is depicted in Figure 4f the conduction band position of **CPP-W** led to a thermodynamic advantage to the reduction of CO₂ comparing with the conduction band position of **CPP-Re**. As we explain in the introduction, tungsten is more abundant, cheaper and less toxic than rhenium, hence these results are relevant in the context of finding sustainable alternatives to using precious and rare transition metals. Until our knowledge, this is the first example of the use of metal organic conjugated porous polymers in continuous mode using water as sacrificial in a gas-phase reactor (Table S5, Supporting Information). Then, these results outperform the state-of-the-art catalytic activity of reported heterogeneous-based polymeric catalysts.

3. Conclusion

We have successfully obtained two stable and efficient heterogeneous photocatalysts for CO₂ reduction by integration of tungsten

and rhenium carbonyl complexes into an organic polymer combining both photosensitizers and catalytic active sites (CPP-Re and CPP-W). Their spectroscopic characterization (IR, NMR, and XANES) shows that Re(I) and W(0) have the same coordination environment to the corresponding molecular Re(dipyridophenazine)(CO)₃Br and W(dipyridophenazine)(CO)₄ complexes. CPP-W and CPP-Re were found active for gas-phase CO₂ photoreduction without any sacrificial agent or metal co-catalyst. It appears that the W-active sites integrated into the CPP network can favor the activation of CO, and then promote its subsequent hydrogenation reaction to achieve CH₄ and C₂H₄. This work provides a new approach for the photoreduction of CO₂ to more electron demanding products catalyzed by porous conjugated polymers modified with single metal sites.

4. Experimental Section

Synthesis of Conjugated Porous Polymers Based on W and Re (CPP-W, CPP-Re): In an Ace pressure 25 mL tube, under inert atmosphere, **2** (30.00 mg, 0.041 mmol, 0.15 eq.), 4,4'-diiodo-1,1'-biphenyl (149 mg, 0.367 mmol, 1.35 eq.) as co-linker, 1,3,5-triphenylbenzene-4',4'',4'''-triboronic acid (119 mg, 0.272 mmol, 1.00 eq.) and the catalyst Pd(PPh₃)₄ (31.4 mg, 0.027 mmol, 0.1 eq.) were added to a mixture of 4 mL DMF and 2 mL THF. The resulting mixture is purged with argon for 20 min and then 2 mL of a previously deoxygenated saturated Cs₂CO₃ solution and 5 mg of K₃PO₄ are added. The mixture was stirred at 150 °C for 4 days. After reaching room temperature, the suspension is filtered and the solid is washed with H₂O, MeOH, THF, DCM, and acetone. Finally, the polymer is treated with H₂O/acetone (4/1) solution of KCN for 24 h to remove Pd(0) residues, then filtered and dried at 110 °C under vacuum. 126 mg of CPP-W was isolated as an air-stable beige solid.

CPP-Re and CPP-Re1 were obtained following a similar method but starting from precursor **3** (135 mg, 0.171 mmol, 0.75 eq. or 55 mg, 0.068 mmol, 0.15 eq.), 4,4'-diiodo-1,1'-biphenyl (69.5 mg, 0.171 mmol, 0.75 eq. or 110 mg, 0.272 mmol, 1.35 eq.), 1,3,5-triphenylbenzene-4',4'',4'''-triboronic acid (100 mg, 0.228 mmol, 1.00 eq.) and Pd(PPh₃)₄ (26.4 mg, 0.023 mmol, 0.1 eq.). CPP-Re and CPP-Re1 were obtained as air-stable orange solids (170 and 130 mg, respectively).

CO₂ Photoreduction Experiments: Gas-phase CO₂ photoreduction experiments were performed in continuous-flow mode using a photoreactor with an effective volume of 280 mL. Powdered samples (20 mg) were deposited on a glass microfiber filter and fitted inside the reactor, which was filled with a mixture of CO₂ (≥99.9999%, Nippon) and water vapor (CO₂: H₂O = 7.25 molar ratio) at 50 °C and 2 bars. The samples were illuminated using four 6 W lamps (λ_{max} = 369 nm) with an average intensity of 47.2 W m⁻² (measured by a Blue-Wave spectrometer). Reaction products were detected in continuous mode with a gas chromatograph (GC, Agilent 7890A) equipped with two separation branches and two sampling loops. First separation branch included two semi-capillary columns (Molsieve 5A and HP Plot Q), a Thermal Conductivity Detector (TCD), a Flame Ionization Detector (FID) and a methanizer. Second separation branch contained a capillary column (CP-Sil 5B) and a second FID. Figure S24 and S25, Supporting Information depicts the chromatograph at different reaction times on both FID detectors

In a typical photocatalytic test, the reactor was degassed under vacuum at 80 °C and then purged with Argon (100 mL min⁻¹ for 1 h) to remove any residual organics weakly adsorbed on the catalyst surface. Then, the catalyst was flushed with the CO₂:H₂O mixture for 1 h to establish an adsorption-desorption balance. Experiments were repeated at least three times to guarantee the reproducibility. No products were detected under dark conditions or under UV illumination without catalyst. Additional control tests were performed under CO₂-free atmospheres and UV illumination (i.e., humid argon (equivalent molar ratio of 7.25 (Ar: H₂O) and argon atmosphere). Again, no carbon products were obtained in any control tests.

Photonic Efficiency (ζ) Calculation: Photonic efficiencies were calculated as the ratio between the rate of reaction and the incident photon flux, according to Equation (1).

$$\zeta = \frac{dN/dt}{\int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} q_{p,\lambda}^0 dt} \quad (1)$$

where dN/dt represents the production rate of products, and q_{p,λ}⁰ is the incident spectral photon flux in the 250–400 nm wavelength range. The incident spectral photon flux was calculated from the lamps emission spectra (see Figure S20, Supporting Information), recorded with a StellarNet UVNB-50 radiometer connected to an optical fibre. The superscript 0 (zero) highlights that the incident number of photons (prior to absorption) is considered.

Photonic Efficiency (ζ) Calculation: Selectivity: Selectivity to C-products were calculated according to Equation (2).

$$S = \frac{\mu \text{ mol of product}}{\text{total } \mu \text{ mol}} \cdot 100 (\%) \quad (2)$$

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available in the supplementary material of this article.

Keywords

CO₂ photoreduction, conjugated porous polymer, phenanthroline polymer, porous phenazine network, rhenium carbonyl, single site, tungsten carbonyl

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